

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR DESIGNING AND TEACHING FUTURE MATHEMATICS TEACHERS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotatsiya:

Ushbu maqolada bugungi kunda kredit-modul sharoitida bo'lajak matematika o'qituvchilarining matematika o'qitish metodikasi fani o'quv mashg'ulotlarini loyihalab o'qitish metodikasi yoritilib ayni vaqtda ta'limning zamonaviy tendentsiyalar jarayonida bo'lajak matematika o'qituvchilarning loyihalab o'qitish mazmuni bayon etlgan hamda tajriba sinov asosida olingan natijalarning samaradorlik darajasi anqlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: *loyihalab o'qitish ko'nikma, pedagogik kompetentsiya, iste'dod, innovatsiya, ijodkorlik, tanqidiy fikrlash, muammolarni hal qilish.*

Аннотация:

В данной статье освещена методика проектирования учебных занятий по математике будущих учителей математики в кредитно-модульных условиях, в то же время изложено содержание проектирования учебных занятий будущих учителей математики в современных тенденциях образования и определен уровень эффективности результатов, полученных на основе экспериментального тестирования.

Ключевые слова: *проектное обучение навыки и умения, педагогическая компетентность, талант, инновации, креативность, критическое мышление, решение проблем.*

Abstract:

This article highlights the methodology of designing mathematics classes for future mathematics teachers in credit-modular conditions, at the same time, the content of designing classes for future mathematics teachers in modern educational trends is outlined and the level of effectiveness of the results obtained on the basis of experimental testing is determined.

Keywords: *project-based learning skills, pedagogical competence, talent, innovation, creativity, critical thinking, problem solving.*

Introduction: Today it is well known that in the practice of developed countries, special attention is paid to the design and organization of educational jarann on the principles of modern educational technologies. But there are certain problems in Uzbekistan when it comes to designing educational jaranni based on the principles of pedagogical technology.

The design of educational work jaraeni on the basis of modern pedagogical and information and Communication Technologies is a factor of educational efficiency. Even if effective work is carried out on the creation of projects based on pedagogical technologies and the organization of educational activities in the

educational system of our country, there are not enough scientifically based templates and guidelines for teaching mathematics. Despite the fact that in most sources the design form of training, the content of the concept of “pedagogical technology” is comprehensively written, the issue of drawing up educational jaraèni projects in mathematics has not found its solution. Therefore, it is appropriate to note that the stages of continuing education, in particular, in the higher education system, the formation of projects of Mathematical Sciences educational jaraè, need research as an urgent pedagogical problem.

During the implementation of this article, the following were identified in this regard:

The composition of educational projects based on the principles of modern pedagogical technology, the essence of educational technology, the availability of resources related to theoretical and practical foundations, special publications, methodological developments and illustrations;

The importance of establishing a system of professional development and popularization of experience of professors and teachers of higher educational institutions, in particular, specialists in the field, in the construction of mathematics teaching projects;

Positive solution of the problem of material and technical support in the design and organization of Education;

The essence of the theory of the creation of educational jaranini projects through the media, focusing on the development of analytical performances on the achievements, experiences gained in the construction and training of mathematical science training projects;

The theory of modern pedagogical technologies and its scientific foundations and Mathematical Sciences in the framework of the possibilities of international donor organizations on education is a high level of Organization of large-scale actions aimed at promoting the creation of projects of educational jaraè.

In higher educational institutions, mathematical sciences are aimed at revealing the theoretical and practical foundations of the introduction of pedagogical technologies in the organization of teaching, creating special guidelines and recommendations for designing and teaching in terms of the narrowness of the scope of scientific research work, etc.

Ensuring that the above problems have a positive solution, teaching mathematics in higher education institutions guarantees jaraèni the success of effective application of modern pedagogical technologies.

It is advisable to carry out the following activities on the construction and training of projects of mathematical disciplines: to create special guides and templates for designing and teaching, to pay special attention to the formation of students ‘ independent working skills;

the material and technical base of educational institutions is provided with technical means of training, equipment, equipment of the audience, equipment for teaching, equipping the rooms where presentations are held (designed for 50-60 students) with multimedia complexes, recommending students to problem situations, devising convenient ways to solve them, updating and enrich didactic

materials on the basis of new information, ; to provide the departments with adequate technical means for the implementation of the necessary educational and methodological complexes, to further improve the system of re-education of professors and teachers in computer literacy and modern pedagogical technologies. a thorough study of regional internal opportunities for the full-fledged implementation of educational technology ideas in educational jaranni; the establishment of measures for the introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies in the teaching of Mathematical Sciences jaraèni and the creation of necessary conditions; re-training of pedagogical workers of all types of educational institutions, improving their skills in the use of new pedagogical technologies and the formation of training design skills; achieving technical literacy of educational subjects; establishing a fast Information Service. The positive solution of these problems makes it possible to educate a competent person and a qualified specialist, in addition to achieving a certain effectiveness in the teaching of Mathematical Sciences jaraèni.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in higher educational institutions in the direction of Pedagogy, the state of teaching the subject “methodology of teaching mathematics” by designing educational activities was studied and analyzed. At the same time, at a certain stage of the system of continuing education, educational institutions, including higher and secondary special, need to research the problem of creating educational jaraèni projects based on the principles of modern pedagogical technology in vocational education as an urgent pedagogical problem.

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